

Outcome of High Dose Oral Prednisolone in Treatment of West Syndrome in Comparison to Low Dose ACTH

Dr. Sk. Serjina Anwar

Junior Consultant, Department of Paediatrics, Kurmitola General Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Dr. Gulsan Ara Jahan

Junior Consultant, Department of Paediatrics, Mugda Medical College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Dr. S. M. Imrul Anwar

Associate Professor, Department of Nephrology, Shaheed M. Monsur Ali Medical College, Sirajganj, Bangladesh

Dr. Sharmina Afrin Sheemu

Medical officer, Department of Paediatric Neurology, National Institute of Neuroscience and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Dr. Gopen Kumar Kundu

Professor, Department of Paediatric Neurology, BSMMU, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract

Introduction: West syndrome is a form of epileptic encephalopathy that typically manifests during infancy, often within the first year of life, and is characterized by developmental regression. Timely identification of its underlying cause and early therapeutic intervention are essential to minimizing the associated morbidity and mortality. The present study aimed to compare the effectiveness of high-dose oral prednisolone with that of intramuscular ACTH in managing West syndrome.

Methods: This quasi-experimental study was carried out in the Department of Paediatric Neurology at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, between September 2021 and August 2022. A total of 80 children diagnosed with West syndrome were enrolled and randomly assigned into two groups: Group A received intramuscular ACTH at a dose of 20 IU/day for two weeks, while Group B was administered oral prednisolone at 4–6 mg/kg/day for the same duration.

Results: A statistically significant reduction in the mean seizure frequency was observed in both the ACTH and oral prednisolone groups following treatment ($P < 0.001$). Normal electroencephalographic findings were achieved in 52.5% of patients in the prednisolone group compared to 32.5% in the ACTH group. Perinatal asphyxia emerged as the predominant etiological factor in both groups (67.5% in the prednisolone group and 80% in the ACTH group). Irritability was the most commonly reported symptom, affecting 50% of the prednisolone group and 60% of the ACTH group.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that both high-dose oral prednisolone and intramuscular ACTH are comparably effective in the treatment of West syndrome. No significant differences were found between the two groups in terms of spasm cessation, normalization of EEG patterns, or incidence of adverse effects.

Introduction

West syndrome (WS) is a rare epileptic condition that affects infants and young children. When the illness struck his son in 1841, Dr. William James West was the

first to describe it [1]. Three symptoms—infantile spasms, developmental regression, and electroencephalogram (EEG) changes—are indicative of West Syndrome. When this debilitating condition

More Information

How to cite this article: Anwar SS, Jahan GA, Anwar SMI, Sheemu SA, Kundu GK. Outcome of High Dose Oral Prednisolone in Treatment of West Syndrome in Comparison to Low Dose ACTH. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(3):142-50.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).22

Keywords:

West syndrome,
Oral prednisolone,
ACTH,
Hypsarhythmia.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

first manifests, neuro-developmental regression takes place and treatment delays may result in poorer consequences [2]. The incidence of WS is 2-3 instances per 10,000 live births, the lifetime prevalence rate is 1.5-2 per 10,000 children and the peak age of onset is 4-6 months [3,4,25]. WS is classified as Symptomatic/Structural- metabolic, Cryptogenic/unknown, and Idiopathic/ Genetic.[5] Epileptic spasms manifest with clusters of a distinct seizure type. [6] The seizures usually consist of sudden, generally bilateral, and symmetrical neck, trunk, and extremities contractions associated with a brief loss of consciousness [7,26].

Seizures usually occur in clusters [8]. West syndrome is provoked by various etiologies such as CNS malformations (focal cortical dysplasia, lissencephaly, holoprosencephaly, callosal agenesis), chromosomal abnormalities (trisomy 21, Miller-Dieker syndrome), neurocutaneous syndrome [27], TORCH infections, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, Birth trauma. Even when the spasms eventually stop, the long-term outlook is not good. Children frequently suffer from Lennox-Gastaut syndrome and other forms of epileptic encephalopathy. The EEG is markedly abnormal in WS. While hypsarrhythmia is present, it may be atypical or altered [9]. Most conventional antiepileptic drugs are ineffective in treating seizures. The first-line therapy for infantile spasms at the moment includes prednisolone with vigabatrin or adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH or Tetracosactoid). The American Academy of Neurology and Child Neurology Association found that low-dose ACTH is equally effective as high-dose ACTH. [10] ACTH is preferred as the first-line treatment in most patients; however, it is expensive and difficult to obtain in some countries [11,28]. As a result, corticosteroids, prednisone, prednisolone, and methylprednisolone, have been used effectively off-label for decades [12,28]. The United Kingdom Infantile Spasms Study (UKISS) revealed no significant differences in treatment outcomes between intramuscular synthetic ACTH (tetracosactide) and oral prednisolone in subgroup analysis [13,28]. Patients and their families can benefit from proof that corticosteroids are an alternative treatment because they are less costly and easier to obtain and administer than ACTH.

So, treatment protocols are varied from clinician to clinician and country to country. Fewer studies are comparing high-dose oral prednisolone (4 mg/kg/day) and low-dose ACTH (20 IU) in the treatment of infantile spasms. Different types of steroids have been used in different centers around the world for West syndrome, but studies regarding the comparison of effectiveness between high-dose oral prednisolone and intramuscular ACTH for the treatment of West syndrome are sparse. Therefore, this study was

conducted to see the response of high-dose oral prednisolone and intramuscular ACTH and compare the drugs' efficacy in children with West syndrome.

Methodology and Materials

This quasi-experimental research was carried out in the Department of Paediatric Neurology, IPNA, at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) in Dhaka, Bangladesh, over a one-year period from September 2021 to August 2022. A total of 80 patients presenting with clinical features indicative of West syndrome were recruited from both the outpatient and inpatient services of the pediatric neurology department at BSMMU [26].

Participants were allocated into two groups: Group A (experimental group), which received treatment with high-dose oral prednisolone, and Group B (control group), which was administered intramuscular ACTH therapy [26].

The following inclusion criteria were applied to determine eligibility for participation in the study:

Inclusion Criteria

- Children with West syndrome of 2 months to 2 years age group.
- EEG findings show hypsarrhythmia or modified hypsarrhythmia
- Parents of children who were willing to participate in the study

Exclusion Criteria

- Age less than 2 months and more than 2 years
- Severely ill patients.
- Patients with status epilepticus
- Previously treated with high-dose oral prednisolone and ACTH.
- Children diagnosed with tuberous sclerosis.

Drug Dosage

Participants in Group A received high-dose oral prednisolone at a dosage of 4–6 mg/kg/day, administered in divided doses over a 2-week period. During this time, patients were closely monitored for potential steroid-related adverse effects. Group B was treated with intramuscular ACTH, administered at a dose of 20 IU once daily, alternating between thighs, for a duration of 2 weeks.

Data Collection Procedure

Study participants were enrolled from both outpatient and inpatient pediatric neurology clinics. Each underwent a thorough baseline assessment that included detailed medical history, neurological examination, and neuroimaging studies such as CT and MRI, along with electroencephalography (EEG). The primary variables assessed were seizure frequency, EEG findings, and the presence of adverse effects, evaluated using standardized assessment tools. Seizure diaries and parental reports were utilized to document seizure frequency before and after treatment. Therapeutic response was assessed at the end of the two-week

treatment period. Institutional protocols were strictly followed in monitoring and managing any adverse reactions. Post-treatment evaluations included continued monitoring of seizure activity and EEG findings. Both prednisolone and ACTH were tapered off over two weeks and discontinued upon achieving clinical remission. In cases where spasms persisted despite tapering, alternative first-line antiepileptic therapies were introduced. Treatment outcomes were categorized as follows: complete remission (absence of seizures or spasms), good response (greater than 50% reduction in seizure/spasm frequency), fair response (25–50% reduction), poor response (0–25% reduction), or no response.

Statistical Analysis

All collected data were systematically documented using a predesigned data collection form. Quantitative variables were reported as means and standard deviations, while qualitative variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Group comparisons

were performed using unpaired t-tests, paired t-tests, chi-square tests, and Fisher’s exact test as appropriate. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 23 for Windows. The study received approval from the Ethical Review Committee of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University.

Results

Table 1 presents the demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the participants. The majority of children in both the high-dose oral prednisolone and ACTH groups were aged 12 months or younger. Male participants outnumbered females in both treatment groups. Perinatal asphyxia emerged as the most frequently identified etiology in both cohorts—accounting for 67.5% in the oral prednisolone group and 80% in the ACTH group. There were no statistically significant differences observed between the two groups in terms of age, sex, body weight, or occipitofrontal circumference (OFC).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Participants in Two Groups (N=80)

	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
Age (months)			
2 - 12	22 (55.0)	22 (55.0)	^a 1.000
13 - 24	18 (45.0)	18 (45.0)	
Mean ± SD	12.06 ± 5.87	12.20 ± 5.83	
Gender			
Male	24 (60.0)	25 (62.5)	^a 0.818
Female	16 (40.0)	15 (37.5)	
Weight	8.18 ± 2.15	8.62 ± 8.64	^b 0.755
Microcephaly	16 (40.0)	18 (45.0)	^a 0.651
Birth related history of the study participants			
Gestational age (weeks)			
Pre term	6 (15.0)	6 (15.0)	^a 0.840
Term	32 (80.0)	33 (82.5)	
Post term	2 (5.0)	1 (2.5)	
Prenatal history			
Fever/rash	1 (10.0)	1 (7.7)	^a 0.734
HTN	3 (30.0)	6 (46.2)	
UTI	6 (60.0)	6 (46.2)	
Perinatal			
Asphyxia	27 (67.5)	32 (80.0)	^a 0.203
Neonatal Jaundice	10 (38.5)	4 (15.4)	
Post-natal			
Neonatal sepsis	13 (50.0)	20 (76.9)	^a 0.094
Meningitis	1 (3.8)	2 (7.7)	
Birth weight			
AGA	26 (65.0)	29 (72.5)	^a 0.564
SGA	11 (27.5)	10 (25.0)	
LGA	3 (7.5)	1 (2.5)	

Note: ^a Chi-Square test and ^b Fisher’s Exact test was done

Table 2: Baseline Seizure Profile of the Study Population in Two Groups (N=80)

	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
Baseline seizure profile			
Age of onset of spasm (months)	5.20 ± 3.22	4.64 ± 2.24	^b 0.367
Type of spasm			
Flexor	18 (45.0)	25 (62.5)	^a 0.243
Extensor	4 (10.0)	4 (10.0)	
Mixed	18 (45.0)	11 (27.5)	
Number of clusters/day	13.12 ± 11.72	17.25 ± 11.63	^b 0.120
Character of spasm			
Symmetric	37 (92.5)	37 (92.5)	^c 1.000
Asymmetric	3 (7.5)	3 (7.5)	
Development history before the spasm			
Age appropriate	8 (20.0)	9 (22.5)	^a 0.785
Delayed	32 (80.0)	31 (77.5)	
Time of started treatment (months)	8.83 ± 5.04	8.40 ± 4.70	^b 0.698
Lag period (months)	5.44 ± 4.95	6.04 ± 5.47	^b 0.610

Note: ^aChi-Square test, ^bUnpaired t-test and ^cFisher’s Exact test were done

Table 2 outlines the clinical characteristics of the participants across the two treatment groups. The average age at spasm onset was 5.20 ± 3.22 months in the high-dose oral prednisolone group and 4.64 ± 2.24 months in the ACTH group, with no statistically significant difference between them (P = 0.367). In the oral prednisolone group, flexor and mixed spasms were

most commonly observed, whereas flexor spasms predominated in the ACTH group. The spasms were symmetrical in 92.5% of cases and asymmetrical in 7.5% across both groups. A history of developmental delay was commonly reported among patients in both cohorts.

Table 3: Associated Impairment of the Study Participant in Two Groups (N=80)

	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
Developmental delay			
Motor	20 (50.0)	14 (35.0)	^a 0.175
Cognition	8(20.0)	7(17.5)	^a 0.775
Vision	4 (10.0)	7 (17.5)	^b 0.330
Hearing	6 (15.0)	3 (7.50)	^b 0.481
Global developmental delay (GDD)	19 (47.5)	23 (57.5)	0.370
Cerebral Palsy (CP)	12 (30.0)	15 (37.5)	0.478
Down syndrome	1 (2.5)	1 (2.5)	^b 1.000
Autism spectrum disorder (ASD)	0	0	

Note: ^aChi-Square test and ^bFisher’s Exact test was done

Table 3 shows the associated impairment of the study subjects in two groups. Global developmental delay was present mostly in both groups (47.5% in the oral prednisolone group and 57.5% in the ACTH group). Other impairments were developmental delay, Cerebral Palsy, and Down Syndrome.

Table 4 shows the CT/MRI findings of the brains of the study subjects in two groups. Cortical atrophy was more prevalent among both groups. Others were encephalomalacia change, Hydrocephalus, Subdural effusion, Corpus callosum agenesis, and Migration defect in the Oral prednisolone group and ACTH group respectively. P value was non-significant in all cases.

Table 4: Neuroimaging Findings (CT/MRI) of the Study Participants in Two Groups (N=80)

	Experimental group (Oral Prednisolone) (n=40)	Control group (ACTH) (n=40)	p-value
Neuroimaging findings			
Normal	1 (2.5)	4 (10.0)	^b 0.359
Abnormal			
Cortical atrophy	21 (52.5)	22 (55.0)	^a 0.823
Calcification	4 (10.0)	1 (2.5)	^b 0.359
Encephalomalacia change	11 (27.5)	16 (40.0)	^a 0.237
Hydrocephalus	4 (10.0)	2 (5.0)	^b 0.396
Subdural effusion	4 (10.0)	1 (2.5)	^b 0.359
Corpus callosum agenesis	2 (5.0)	1 (2.5)	^b 1.000
Migration defect	0 (0.0)	1 (2.5)	^b 1.000
Others	0 (0.0)	2 (5.0)	^b 1.000

Note: ^a Chi-Square test and ^b Fisher’s Exact test was done

Table 5: Response to Therapy of Study Subjects in Two Groups (N=80)

Response of the therapy		Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
Response	Complete 21(52.5%)			
	Good 10 (25%)	31 (77.5)	25 (62.5)	0.222
No response	Fair 8 (20.0%)			
	No response 1 (5.0)	9 (22.5)	15 (37.5)	0.222

Note: Complete (No seizure), Good (> 50% seizure reduction), fair (< 50% seizure reduction), None (No response).

Table 5 shows the response to therapy between the two groups. Response to the treatment was found in 31 (77.5 %) patients in the Oral prednisolone group and 25 (62.5%) in the ACTH group. No statistical significance was detected between the two groups, with p value of 0.222.

Table 6 shows that the onset of response to treatment was significantly earlier in the oral Prednisolone group

than ACTH group. 52.5% in the Oral prednisolone group and 30% in the ACTH group responded within 10 days. (P value 0.041). The mean seizure frequency before therapy of oral prednisolone was 13.42±11.60, and after therapy was 4.52±6.45. In the ACTH group before therapy mean was found 18.42±11.8 and after therapy mean was 6.02±6.39. In both groups frequency of seizures was significantly reduced. P value <0.001.

Table 6: Median Duration of Spasm Resolution & Frequency of Seizure after Therapy in Two Groups (N=80)

Median duration for spasm resolution	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
<10 days	21 (52.5)	12 (30.0)	0.041
≥ 10 days	19 (47.5)	28 (70.0)	
Frequency of seizure (Mean ± SD)			
Before therapy	13.42±11.60	18.42±11.8	
After therapy	4.52±6.45	6.02±6.39	
P-value	<0.001	<0.001	

Table 7: Response to Therapy between Symptomatic and Unknown Variety of West Syndrome of Study Subjects in Two Groups (N=80)

Neuroimaging	Experimental Group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)			Control group ACTH (n=40)		
	Response	No response	p-value	Response	No response	p-value
Unknown	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1.000	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	0.602
Symptomatic	29 (74.4)	10 (25.6)		24 (66.7)	12 (33.3)	

Table 7 shows the response of therapy between the Unknown and Symptomatic variety of West syndrome and found no statistical difference between the two groups. In the case of Oral prednisolone P value was

1.000 and in the case of the ACTH group P value was 0.602.

Table 8 shows the EEG response before and after therapy. EEG status significantly improved in both the Oral prednisolone and ACTH groups, P value <0.001.

Table 8: EEG Response before and after Therapy (N=80)

EEG	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)			Control group ACTH (n=40)		
	Before therapy	After therapy	p-value	Before therapy	After therapy	p-value
Normal	0	21 (52.5)	<0.001	0	13 (32.5)	<0.001
Abnormal	40 (100.0)	19 (47.5)		40 (100.0)	27 (67.5)	

Note: A marginal homogeneity test was done

Table 9: Adverse Effect of the Patients in Two Groups after Treatment (N=80)

Adverse effect	Experimental group Oral Prednisolone (n=40)	Control group ACTH (n=40)	p-value
Cushingoid appearance	8 (20.0)	4 (10.0)	^b 0.210
Hypertension	6 (15.0)	12 (30.0)	^a 0.108
Increased appetite	19 (47.5)	11 (27.5)	^a 0.065
Weight gain	19 (47.5)	15 (37.5)	^a 0.366
Irritability	20 (50.0)	24 (60.0)	^a 0.369
GIT upset	12 (30.0)	13 (32.5)	^a 0.809
Hyperglycemia	0 (0.0)	3 (7.5)	^b 0.241
Others	0 (0.0)	1 (2.5)	^b 1.000

Note: ^a Chi-Square test and ^b Fisher’s Exact test was done

Table 9 shows that maximum patients had irritability, 50% of the Oral prednisolone group and 60% of the ACTH group followed by weight gain (47.5% & 37.5%) and GIT upset 30% and 32.5% in oral prednisolone and ACTH group respectively. Other less frequent adverse effects showed were Cushingoid appearance, Hypertension, and increased appetite. No significant difference was noted [25].

Discussion

This quasi-experimental study aimed to assess the effectiveness of high-dose oral prednisolone compared to intramuscular (IM) ACTH in the treatment of West syndrome among the study population in a tertiary care center in Bangladesh [25].

In the present study, the average age of the study children was 12.06 ± 5.87 months in the oral prednisolone group and 12.20 ± 5.83 months in the ACTH group. Males were the most common gender in both groups. Other two studies by Khreisat et al also found male predominance [15,26].

In this study, it was found perinatal asphyxia is more common in both groups. Wanigasinghe et al and Basit A et al showed the underlying symptomatic cause is hypoxic ischemic injury [16,17]. In this study, most of the study participants had delayed development before spasm 32/40 (80 %) in the oral prednisolone group and 31/40 (77.5%) in the ACTH group. Microcephaly was found in 16(40%) & 18 (45%) in the oral prednisolone

and ACTH group respectively. This result had similarities with a study performed in Jordan by Khreisat et al. [15]. In this study, spasms started between 3-5 months of age in both groups. Similarly, Khreisat et al reported in their study that, the mean age onset of seizure was 9.4 months which was higher than our study [15]. In the study most common type of seizure was both flexor and mixed type. Chellamuthu, P et al show most of the spasms were flexor type [18]. After treatment, the seizure frequency was improved significantly and it was 4.52±6.45 in the oral prednisolone group and 6.02±6.39 in the ACTH group and found statistically significant <0.001. Chellamuthu P et al also showed significant improvement in seizure frequency after high-dose oral prednisolone therapy (4mg/kg) [18].

Neuroimaging findings show that 39 patients out of 40 patients had a structural abnormality in the oral prednisolone group and 36 patients in the ACTH group. From which cortical atrophy is more prevalent. Another study done by Chellamuthu et al also found the same abnormality [18].

In the study participants, complete cessation of spasm occurred 21/40, (52.5 %) in the oral prednisolone group and 13/40 (32.5%) in the ACTH group. When categorized as a response to therapy it was a total of 77.5% in the case of oral prednisolone and 62.5% in the ACTH group. No significant difference was detected

between the two groups in terms of response to therapy. Although complete cessation of spasm was more 21 (52.5%) in the oral prednisolone group than in ACTH group 13 (32.5%). These findings are very similar to what was reported by Chellamuthu et al where the low-dose prednisolone group reported a complete response in 25% of cases in comparison to 51.6% in the high-dose prednisolone group ($p=0.03$) [18,29]. The UKISS reported a high proportion of infants (70.0%) achieving spasm freedom in the oral prednisolone group [20] Kossoff et al reported the high-dose oral prednisolone group as having complete spasm cessation in 67% of infants, whereas EEG findings were also normal in 70% of cases using high-dose prednisolone [21,29]. Hancock and Osborne found that 71.4% of infants having complete spasm freedom by the end of 14 days were on the high-dose prednisolone regimen [6,29]. Complete spasm freedom is reported in the present study among 52.5 % of cases using high-dose prednisolone, which is somewhat lower than what has been reported in earlier studies [29].

In this study, the median duration of spasm resolution was categorized as <10 days, and >10 days. In the oral prednisolone group 21/40 (52.5%) and in the ACTH group 12/40 (30%) had their median duration of spasm resolution within 10 days. Duration of response was significantly earlier in the oral Prednisolone group than ACTH group (P value 0.041). However, a higher proportion of patients in ACTH group 28/40 (70%) had their spasm resolution occur in >10. One study performed by Chellamuthu et al showed that 51.6% of patients responded within 14 days [18] and in another study by Iype, M. et al found that 20% of patients responded within 14 days who took ACTH [22]. Our result is not consistent with their study.

In this study, we see the response between symptomatic and unknown groups, no statistically significant difference was noted in both groups. If the sample size is high then the results may be statistically significant. The UKISS research by Lux et al. and the study by Singhi and Ray revealed no difference in spasm cessation rates between the two groups [20,23,30]. However, Lagae et al found a better spasm cessation outcome in the cryptogenic group as compared to the symptomatic group [24,30].

When we compared the EEG response in both groups before and after therapy we found significant improvement in both groups, p -value <0.001. A study done by Wanigasinghe et al showed that the prednisolone group showed a significantly greater improvement in severity than that of the ACTH group (7.95 ± 2.76 vs 6.00 ± 2.61 ; $p < 0.01$). This study is the first randomized clinical trial to show the superiority of prednisolone over ACTH for the treatment of West syndrome from the perspective of improvement of hypsarrhythmia (EEG response) [16,25].

In this study, the commonly found adverse effects were irritability, GIT upset, weight gain, increased appetite, cushingoid appearance, and hypertension. Most patients in both groups were presented with irritability, 50% in the case of the Oral prednisolone group and 60% in the case of the ACTH group. Chellamuthu et al showed weight gain and cushingoid facies were the most common adverse effects in their study participants [18,25].

Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted at a single center, with a limited sample size owing to the brief duration of the research period. Long-term follow-up of the participants was not carried out, and as a result, potential long-term factors or interventions that could influence outcomes remain unknown.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study demonstrated that both high-dose oral prednisolone and intramuscular (IM) ACTH therapy were comparably effective in managing West syndrome. There were no statistically significant differences between the two treatment modalities in terms of seizure frequency reduction, EEG improvements, or treatment-related side effects. Nevertheless, the initiation of therapeutic response occurred notably earlier in the group receiving oral prednisolone compared to the ACTH group. Therefore, to substantiate these findings, additional research employing randomized clinical trial designs with larger patient populations is warranted.

Funding

No funding sources.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

References

- [1] West WJ. On a peculiar form of infantile convulsions. *Lancet*. 1841;35(911):724–5.
- [2] Kivity S, Lerman P, Ariel R, Danziger Y, Mimouni M, Shinnar S. Long-term cognitive outcomes of a cohort of children with cryptogenic infantile spasms treated with high-dose adrenocorticotrophic hormone. *Epilepsia*. 2004 Mar;45(3):255–62. doi: 10.1111/j.0013-9580.2004.32003.x.
- [3] Riikonen R. Epidemiological data of West syndrome in Finland. *Brain Dev*. 2001 Nov;23(7):539–41. doi: 10.1016/s0387-7604(01)00263-7.
- [4] Trevathan E, Murphy CC, Yeargin-Allsopp M. The descriptive epidemiology of infantile spasms among Atlanta children. *Epilepsia*. 1999 Jun;40(6):748–51. doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1157.1999.tb00773.x.
- [5] Taghdiri MM, Nemati H. Infantile spasm: a review article. *Iran J Child Neurol*. 2014 Summer;8(3):1–5.

- [6] Hancock EC, Osborne JP, Edwards SW. Treatment of infantile spasms. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2013 Jun 5;(6):CD001770. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD001770.pub3.
- [7] Pellock JM, Hrachovy R, Shinnar S, Baram TZ, Bettis D, Dlugos DJ, et al. Infantile spasms: a US consensus report. *Epilepsia.* 2010 Oct;51(10):2175–89. doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1167.2010.02657.x.
- [8] Nash K, Sullivan J. Myoclonic seizures and infantile spasms. In: Swaiman KF, Ashwal S, Ferriero DM, Schor NF, editors. *Swaiman's Pediatric Neurology: Principles and Practice.* 5th ed. Edinburgh: Elsevier Saunders; 2012. p. 774–89.
- [9] Go CY, Mackay MT, Weiss SK, Stephens D, Adams-Webber T, Ashwal S, et al. Evidence-based guideline update: medical treatment of infantile spasms: report of the Guideline Development Subcommittee of the American Academy of Neurology and the Practice Committee of the Child Neurology Society. *Neurology.* 2012 Jun 12;78(24):1974–80. doi: 10.1212/WNL.0b013e318259e2cf.
- [10] Fusco L, Vigeveno F. Ictal clinical electroencephalographic findings of spasms in West syndrome. *Epilepsia.* 1993 Jul-Aug;34(4):671–8. doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1157.1993.tb00491.x.
- [11] Azam M, Bhatti N, Krishin J. Use of ACTH and prednisolone in infantile spasms: experience from a developing country. *Seizure.* 2005 Dec;14(8):552–6. doi: 10.1016/j.seizure.2005.08.005.
- [12] Wilmshurst JM, Gaillard WD, Vinayan KP, Tsuchida TN, Plouin P, Van Bogaert P, et al. Summary of recommendations for the management of infantile seizures: Task Force Report for the ILAE Commission of Pediatrics. *Epilepsia.* 2015 Aug;56(8):1185–97. doi: 10.1111/epi.13057.
- [13] Lux AL, Edwards SW, Hancock E, Johnson AL, Kennedy CR, Newton RW, et al. The United Kingdom Infantile Spasms Study (UKISS) comparing hormone treatment with vigabatrin on developmental and epilepsy outcomes to age 14 months: a multicentre randomised trial. *Lancet Neurol.* 2005 Nov;4(11):712–7. doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(05)70215-1.
- [14] Krijgh EJC, Catsman-Berrevoets CE, Neuteboom RF. Early seizure freedom is a prognostic factor for survival in patients with West syndrome. *Neuropediatrics.* 2018 Aug;49(4):279–82. doi: 10.1055/s-0038-1654708.
- [15] Khreisat WH. Clinical profile of infants with hypsarrhythmia. *Acta Inform Med.* 2011 Sep;19(3):149–52. doi: 10.5455/aim.2011.19.149-152.
- [16] Wanigasinghe J, Arambepola C, Ranganathan SS, Sumanasena S, Muhandiram EC. The efficacy of moderate-to-high dose oral prednisolone versus low-to-moderate dose intramuscular corticotropin for improvement of hypsarrhythmia in West syndrome: a randomized, single-blind, parallel clinical trial. *Pediatr Neurol.* 2014 Jul;51(1):24–30. doi: 10.1016/j.pediatrneurol.2014.03.012.
- [17] Basit A, Noreen N, Saleem SF, Yousuf M, Zafar F. Comparison of efficacy and safety of low-versus high-dose oral prednisolone in infantile spasm (IS): an open-label randomized controlled trial at the Children's Hospital & Institute of Child Health, Multan, Pakistan. *Cureus.* 2022 Mar 14;14(3):e23164. doi: 10.7759/cureus.23164.
- [18] Chellamuthu P, Sharma S, Jain P, Kaushik JS, Seth A, Aneja S. High-dose (4 mg/kg/day) versus usual dose (2 mg/kg/day) oral prednisolone for treatment of infantile spasms: an open-label, randomized controlled trial. *Epilepsy Res.* 2014 Aug;108(8):1378–84. doi: 10.1016/j.eplepsyres.2014.06.008.
- [19] Keshave A, Yende-Zuma N, Mubaiwa L, Adhikari M. The clinical profile and outcome of children with West syndrome in KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa: A 10-year retrospective review. *S Afr J Child Health.* 2017 Sep;11(3):135–40. doi: 10.7196/SAJCH.2017.v11i3.1296.
- [20] Lux AL, Edwards SW, Hancock E, Johnson AL, Kennedy CR, Newton RW, et al. The United Kingdom Infantile Spasms Study comparing vigabatrin with prednisolone or tetracosactide at 14 days: a multicentre, randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2004 Nov 13;364(9447):1773–8. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(04)17442-3.
- [21] Kossoff EH. Infantile spasms. *Neurologist.* 2010 Mar;16(2):69–75. doi: 10.1097/NRL.0b013e3181d8c2b6.
- [22] Iype M, Saradakutty G, Kunju PAM, Mohan D, Nair MKC, George B, et al. Infantile spasms: A prognostic evaluation. *Ann Indian Acad Neurol.* 2016 Apr-Jun;19(2):228–32. doi: 10.4103/0972-2327.182312.
- [23] Singhi P, Ray M. Profile of West syndrome in North Indian children. *Brain Dev.* 2005 Mar;27(2):135–40. doi: 10.1016/j.braindev.2004.05.002.
- [24] Lagae L, Verhelst H, Ceulemans B, De Meirleir L, Nassogne MC, De Borchgrave V, et al. Treatment and long-term outcome in West syndrome: the clinical reality. A multicentre follow-up study. *Seizure.* 2010 Apr;19(3):159–64. doi: 10.1016/j.seizure.2010.01.003.
- [25] Anwar SS, Kundu GK, Anwar SMI, Jahan GA, Khanum M, Sheemu SA, et al. Pattern of EEG change after treatment with high dose oral prednisolone in comparison to low dose ACTH among children with West syndrome in a tertiary care hospital. *ARC J Pediatr.* 2024;9(2):29–36. doi:10.20431/2455-5711.0902005.
- [26] Hancock EC, Osborne JP, Edwards SW. Treatment of infantile spasms. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2002;(2):CD001770. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD001770.

[27] Chandra M, Saha N, Hoque SA, Sarkar PK, Begum SA, Mistry B. Clinical and laboratory profiles of children with West syndrome: experience of 50 cases in a tertiary hospital in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh J Child Health*. 2020;44(3):139–42. doi:10.3329/bjch.v44i3.52704.

[28] Chang YH, Chen C, Chen SH, Shen YC, Kuo YT. Effectiveness of corticosteroids versus adrenocorticotrophic hormone for infantile spasms: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Clin Transl Neurol*. 2019;6(11):2270–81. doi:10.1002/acn3.50922.

[29] Basit A, Noreen N, Saleem SF, Yousuf M, Zafar F. Comparison of efficacy and safety of low-versus high-

dose oral prednisolone in infantile spasm (IS): an open-label randomized controlled trial at the Children's Hospital & Institute of Child Health, Multan, Pakistan. *Cureus*. 2022;14(3):e23164. doi:10.7759/cureus.23164.

[30] Chellamuthu P, Sharma S, Jain P, Kaushik JS, Seth A, Aneja S. High-dose (4 mg/kg/day) versus usual dose (2 mg/kg/day) oral prednisolone for treatment of infantile spasms: an open-label, randomized controlled trial. *Epilepsy Res*. 2014;108(8):1378–84. doi:10.1016/j.epilepsyres.2014.06.019.

